

A 3D PRINTED PLA FRESNEL SUBSTRATE LENS APPLIED ON THE UWB PALM TREE ANTIPODAL VIVALDI ANTENNA TO PROVIDE ULTRA DIRECTIVITY FOR ANTI-UAV DEFENSE

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Abstract - This work presents an ultra-wideband (UWB) antenna of the Palm Tree (PT-AVA) Vivaldi Antipodal, equipped with a Fresnel substrate lens (Fresnel SL). The lens is made of Polylactic Acid Plastic (PLA) using a 3D printing technique. When the results of directivity of the Palm Tree with Fresnel Lens (Fresnel PT-AVA) are compared with those of the one without the lens, there are improvements in the directivity characteristics, namely: increase of the main lobe gain (ML), as well as the reduction of its angular aperture and reduction of lateral lobe level (SLL). The measurements show that at 3 GHz there is an improvement in gain to 11.5 dB and a reduction to -6.4 dB SLL, in contrast to only 7.9 dB gain and -5.3 dB SLL of the antenna Palm Tree without the lens. The application of this lens corrected the strabismus of 3° and reduced the angular aperture from 40° to 24.7°.

Keywords: PLA; Fresnel lens; Antenna Vivaldi, UWB, Palm Tree.

I. INTRODUCTION

Increasing use of drones or unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) poses significant threats to public safety and personal privacy [1]. UAVs can be employed to fly over airport airspace and cause accidents, invade privacy by collecting images with a camera, smuggle illicit components between countries, or even be armed with explosives for terrorist attacks [1]-[5].

Whether controlled by malicious groups or amateur individuals, the rising frequency of incidents involving UAVs necessitates the use of anti-UAV systems to regulate drone air traffic. To compose such systems, it is important to utilize a highly directive antenna with ultra-wideband (UWB) capabilities, operating across the various radio frequency (RF) signals that UAVs communicate on, typically in the IEEE 802.11 communication standard [1].

Achieving the necessary directivity and UWB operation, anti-UAV systems employ two or more antennas, making their construction more complex. For this purpose, this investigation explores the radiation enhancement of Vivaldi antennas (VA). They can be classified in two distinct ways: coplanar (CVA) [6] and antipodal (AVA) [7]. Over the last few decades, these antennas have been a focus of attention, mainly due to their sui generis characteristics, that is, it is an UWB antenna, compact architecture, endfire, simplified design and construction, with high gain and can be directly integrated into a printed circuit board [8] - [16].

Despite high expectation on these characteristics, AVA in its original design retains some intrinsic problems of its design, for example

the subtle unbalance of currents in its two (different) conducting surfaces, which promotes the deviation of the directivity of the main lobe) of the order of many degrees, as well as a high-level SLL.

The PT-AVA, proposed in [17], corrects these problems by promoting the control of surface currents on the sides of the antenna with slot notch in exponential form, or Exponential Slot Edge (ESE). As this antenna almost totally adds energy to the main lobe, it is a strong candidate for the application of substrate lenses (SL), to further improve its gain and directivity characteristics. Therefore, it is proposed here the addition of a 3D Fresnel substrate lens made in PLA (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Photograph of the proposed Fresnel Substrate Lens, applied on a Palm Tree AVA (PT-AVA).

When comparing the antennas, at the frequency of 3 GHz, PT-AVA and Fresnel PT-AVA, it was observed that the SLL was reduced from -5.3 dB to -6.4 dB, and related to strabismus (squint), from 3° to 0°, respectively. Regarding the gain of the main

lobe, Fresnel PT-AVA achieves a gain approximately 2 times larger, when compared to the original PT-AVA, that is, 11.5 dB compared to 7.9 dB. These characteristics make the Fresnel PT-AVA excellent for anti-UAV applications, achieving a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of 0 dBm at 20 m from the UAV.

In order to better demonstrate this new substrate lens technology in Fresnel form, this work was divided as follows: Section II presents the methodology of electric characterization of the substrate. Section III presents the Fresnel PT-AVA design and development (R & D). The simulated and experimental results are discussed in Section IV. Section V presents the results obtained from the proof-of-concept as an anti-UAV defense jammer and, finally, Section VI contemplates the conclusions and final arguments.

II. SUBSTRATE CHARACTERIZATION

A. Lens Manufacturing Methodology With 3D Printer

The 3D additive printing technique uses an extrusion of plastic material. With this technique, the geometric and thermal parameters of the printing can be varied, which influences the PLA-air ratio and, consequently, the density of the printed part, which promotes the control of its relative electrical permittivity to the vacuum ϵ_r (relative dielectric constant). The use of 3D printers has led to great interest in antenna research and propagation [18], [19], [20]. We chose the use of a Prusa Mendel I2 3D printer, equipped with a 1.75mm filament of Polylactic Acid (PLA), for the construction of the Fresnel lens.

To perform the printing, the following parameters were adjusted: The thickness of each layer was 200 μm ; the fill rate was 100%, that is, fully filled by PLA; the deposition rate was 50 mm/s; the power of the central cooling system (CCS) of the printed part by ventilation has been set at 100%. The base chosen to promote the best adhesion of the part and to avoid the WARP effect (detachment and deformation of the part by cooling), was of type RAFT. The first layers were printed at a speed of 20 mm/s while the power of the CCS was set at 30% to also minimize the WARP effect.

The dot size was adjusted to 390 μm and the retraction velocity of the filament was adjusted to 40 mm/s. During printing, the base was maintained at a temperature of 70 $^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 3\%$ and the Hotend at a temperature of 200 $^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2\%$.

B. PLA Dielectric Constant Characterization

This subsection describes the method used to determine the permittiveness of a PLA sample. As discussed in the previous subsection (A), the 3D printing technique, based on the extrusion of plastic

material, allows to vary the geometric and thermal parameters of the printing, which influences the PLA-air ratio and the density of the printed part. This allowed to determine ϵ_r . Therefore, to determine the ϵ_r of the SL substrate, six plates, with dimensions of 100mm \times 40mm and a thickness of 1.6mm were printed, all in PLA and with the same parameters used during SL printing.

On one side of each plate, a thin sheet of copper was glued, while on the other side a 4 mm wide microstrip line was glued longitudinally, centered and with a total length of 100 mm.

A small stub of copper foil, 2mm \times 10mm in size, was then glued in the middle of the micro-line to produce a planar T-type resonator, proposed in the ϵ_r characterization technique [21], according to Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Design of the planar T-type resonator in PLA proposed by ref. [21].

This is an open quarter-wavelength resonator ($l = \lambda_g/4$, with λ_g representing the guided wavelength). In it, the input impedance Z_{in} is calculated as a function of the characteristic impedance Z_0 , according to:

$$Z_{in} = -jZ_0 \cot(\beta l) \quad (1)$$

where β represents the wave number ($2\pi/\lambda$). For the specific frequencies where l equals odd multiples of $\lambda/4$, equation (1) results in equation (2):

$$Z_{in} = -jZ_0 \cot\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = 0 \quad (2)$$

This means that the open circuit, on the stump, behaves in the connection with the micro-line as a short circuit - only for those resonant frequencies - preventing reflection (energy remaining in the resonator) from reaching the connector. Frequencies outside this resonant range will directly couple between the two ends of the micro-line, since the resonator will be an open transmission line.

The same model is digitally constructed in an electromagnetic simulation (EM) environment. Through the EM simulation process, the parameter ϵ_{rsim} can be swept until the simulated S parameters are adjusted to those obtained from the measurement. It is important to ensure that the coaxial connectors (SMA) are correctly modeled in the simulation because they add parasitic effects to the model.

Thus, to determine the ϵ_r of the PLA to be used in the construction of Fresnel SL, five samples were tested, three of black PLA, one of yellow PLA and

Fig. 3. Design of the antenna and its parameters: (a) Top view (xz-plane) of the AVA reference. (b) Top view of Fresnel Palm Tree AVA. (c) Detail of the second quadrant of the proposed Fresnel substrate lens.

one of blue PLA. The results obtained from the planar T-resonator method are presented in Table I.

TABLE I – CHARACTERIZATION RESULTS FROM THE PLANAR RESSONER METHOD [21] OF THE DIFFERENT SAMPLES OF PLA BETWEEN 0-3.5 GHz.

Sample	Material	ϵ_r
Sample #1	Yellow PLA	2.6
Sample #2	White PLA	2.6
Sample #3	White PLA	2.6
Sample #4	Blue PLA	2.6
Sample #5	White PLA	2.7

To confirm the results obtained with the planar T resonator technique, a comparison was made with the results of Elsallal et al. [25], which determined ϵ_r and loss tangent using the coaxial technique from 0 to 18 GHz, obtaining mean values of 2.75 for ϵ_r and 0.015 for loss tangent, when four different samples were tested.

Fig. 4 shows the values of ϵ_r and loss tangent obtained by [22] from the four samples test, between 0 and 3.5 GHz, indicating mean values of respectively 2.8 and 0.028 for ϵ_r and loss tangent. Therefore, for the Fresnel SL project, the value of 2.6 for ϵ_r was adopted.

Fig. 4. Electrical properties measured from extruded PLA samples using Voxel8 printer [22].

III. DESIGN OF THE FRESNEL PT-AVA

Fig. 3 (a) shows details of the conventional AVA design, while Fig. 3 (b) shows Fresnel PT-AVA design details. Fig. 3 (c) shows the details of Fresnel SL and the table with construction parameters.

The Palm Tree AVA for the application of Fresnel SL was chosen because of its high directivity. Additionally, the lateral notches in the Exponential form (ESE) soften the interface between the metal (edges) and the medium (air) [17], performing a similar role of an array of "parasitic" antennas and guiding the energy of the lateral lobes, which is potentially collimated by Fresnel SL, to ML. Another antenna that uses this technique of resonant cavities is the FSE-AVA [23].

This collimation of the ML energy provided an increase in gain to 11.4 dB, in contrast to the 7.9 dB gain of the reference PT-AVA. This antenna can also be miniaturized when using substrates with high dielectric constant (ϵ_r), such as Alumina, or LTCC for example.

The antenna is constructed with the substrate FR4, which has ϵ_r of 4.3 and loss tangent of 0.025, with a thickness of 1.6 mm. The exponential aperture was idealized according to the curve proposed by [17], whose equation is defined as the aperture rate R of 0.038.

The Fresnel SL was glued on the Palm Tree antenna with a 3M™ double-sided tape.

IV. SIMULATEDS AND MEASURED RESULTS

The Fresnel Palm Tree AVA was designed in three stages: in the first and second, the antenna and Fresnel SL characteristics were optimized, respectively, by numerical simulations.

Fig. 5. E-Field Distribution Diagram in the xz plane of the Fresnel Palm Tree AVA at 3GHz.

TABLE II - COMPARISON OF THE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE 3 GHz ANTENNA: GAIN, SLL, STRASS AND ANGLE OPENING.

	PT-AVA	Fresnel PT-AVA
Gain [dB]	7.9	11.4
SLL [dB]	-5.3	-6.4
Squint [°]	3.0	0.0
Angular Open [°]	40	24.7

Fig. 6. Loss and return curves (S11) measured and simulated.

In the third stage, the manufacture and experimental measurements of the antenna prototype were carried out, with the optimized parameters, thus obtaining the gain, the S-parameters and the radiation pattern. Table II presents a comparison between the Fresnel Palm Tree AVA proposed, and the PT-AVA (without lens) reference. In terms of gain and angular width, the Fresnel PT-AVA is considerably more efficient than the reference PT-AVA, since the lens promotes beam collimation. Despite this fact, the ESE's continue to promote the reduction of SLL and the increase of ML.

The return loss curve (S11) is shown in Fig. 6.

Due to the control of the surface currents on the side of the antenna, promoted in the PT-AVA, through the use of the lateral radiators (ESE), a simultaneous reduction of SLL and the increase in ML is promoted. This guarantees the efficiency of Fresnel SL use, since the energy of the ML passes almost completely through the lens, in addition to correcting the effect of strabismus (squint). The improved directivity observed in the Fresnel PT-AVA comes from harnessing the energy that would be radiated to the lateral lobes, which usually occurs in a conventional AVA, making the use of substrate lenses less effective.

Fig. 5 shows the distribution of Antenna E-Fields, in the xz-plane, where there is no distribution in the lateral direction, low SLL, due to the control of surface currents at the edges of the antenna, characteristic of the Palm Tree AVA.

Fig. 7. PT-AVA Measured and Simulated Radiation Diagrams with and without Fresnel SL at 3 GHz.

Still in analyzing the illustration of the Electric Field distribution diagram of Fig. 6, it is clear that the interaction between the fields and the lens leads to beam collimation. This interaction promotes the

ultra-directivity of the antenna and, consequently, a gain of 11.4 dB in ML. In addition, the use of the Fresnel SL lens simultaneously promotes the reduction to -6.4 dB of SLL and the 3-degree correction of the strabismus effect. Fig. 7 shows the radiation patterns of PT-AVA with and without Fresnel SL at 3 GHz.

V. ANTI-UAV APPLICATIONS RESULTS

To prove the concept of the Fresnel PT-AVA anti-UAV applications, an indoor test setup was assembled. In this setup, a Fern-AVA [24] performed spectral analysis of the Fresnel PT-AVA's jamming with the drone, transmitting noise at 2.417 GHz, the UAV's communication frequency, thereby disrupting the UAV's proper functioning.

To generate this noise, the Fresnel PT-AVA was connected to a microwave signal generator, and the proper positioning of the antenna was ensured using an electronic tape measure, the LV 56 model from LomVum & Miliseey, and an electronic level meter, the L52 Multifunctional Cross Marking Level model from Miliseey, determining the distance and alignment between the Fresnel PT-AVA and the target, respectively.

To avoid external noise interference with the UAV's communication, it was fixed on a foam support inside a semi-anechoic chamber composed of 24" x 12" x 4"H light blue absorber panels, the Slab Absorber model from AEMI - A Microwave Vision Company, as shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. UAV on a styrofoam support inside the semi-anechoic chamber.

Fig. 9 shows the measurements taken during the UAV jamming at the four presented distances. From these results, it can be observed that as the Fresnel PT-AVA was moved away from the target, the noise generated in the UAV's communication signal decreased.

Fig. 9. Jamming performed by the Fresnel PT-AVA at 5, 10, 15, and 20 m.

The data presented in Fig. 9 can be applied to the SNR relationship in dBm, given by equation (3) [25], [26]:

$$SNR = S - N \quad (3)$$

Where S and N represent, respectively, the measured signal and noise. Thus, Table III presents the SNR results for the measurements shown in Figure 9.

TABLE III - SNR CALCULATED FROM THE DATA OBTAINED IN THE PROOF OF CONCEPT.

Distance [m]	S [dBm]	N [dBm]	SNR [dBm]
5.0	40.0	60.0	-20.0
10.0	40.0	55.0	-15.0
15.0	40.0	50.0	-10.0
20.0	40.0	40.0	0.0

With the SNRs presented in Table III, it can be observed that the strongest jamming occurred at 5 m, and as the antenna was moved away, the impact of the noise on the UAV decreased. Additionally, the table confirms that the concept works perfectly to inhibit the communication between the controller and the UAV, as an SNR below 40 dBm indicates high interference in the studied signal.

VI. SUMMARY

This research presents a new Fresnel substrate lens (Fresnel SL) printed in 3D with PLA for applications in PT-AVA (Palm Tree AVA), in order to improve the radiation pattern (directivity) in an unprecedented way. The application of this lens simultaneously promotes the attenuation of the Lateral Lobe Level, increases the gain of the Main Lobe and reduces the angular width, as well as strabismus.

When comparing the Fresnel PT-AVA with the reference PT-AVA (without lens), it is observed in simulations and experimental results, at 3 GHz, that there is a better gain of 11.4 dB, while PT-AVA without lens has a gain of 7.9 dB. In terms of SLL, it improved to -6.4 dB, corresponding to a reduction of 1.1 dB with respect to PT-AVA. The angular aperture was reduced from 40 to 24.7 degrees, and he totally corrected his strabismus, with a correction of 3 degrees. In addition to generating effective noise in anti-UAV applications, it exhibits an SNR of -20, -15, -10 and 0 dBm for distances of 5, 10, 15

and 20 m between the UAV and the Fresnel PT-AVA, respectively. All these results indicate that the addition of Fresnel SL to PT-AVA contributed significantly to an increase in directivity.

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